

The Impact of Corporate Brand Reputation on Customer Satisfaction, Loyalty, and Retention: An ANOVA-Based Analysis of Age and Service Tenure Among Vodacom Customers in South Africa

Author(s) and Affiliations

Dr. Kubashen Naidoo, DBA, MBA, MPhil ×2, CBAP

Independent Researcher, Author, and Business Coach
South Africa

Email: knaidoo1980@gmail.com

Tel: +27 84 850 0631

Dr. Navalpreet Kaur

Associate Professor – Research Programs
UniAthena India Pvt. Ltd.

Email: navalpreet@uniathena.com | dr.navalpreetkaur@gmail.com

Tel: +91 77197 68089

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Notes on Authors

Dr. Kubashen Naidoo is an independent researcher and business coach with expertise in strategic brand development, customer experience, and business transformation. He holds multiple postgraduate degrees and certifications, and his work focuses on bridging academic insight with practical business impact in emerging markets.

Dr. Navalpreet Kaur is an Associate Professor at UniAthena India Pvt. Ltd., specializing in research methodology, strategic management, and consumer behavior. She has published extensively and mentors doctoral candidates across global programs.

Abstract

This study explores Vodacom's corporate brand reputation strategy in South Africa's telecommunications sector, focusing on its impact on customer satisfaction, loyalty, and retention. Data from 389 Vodacom users were analysed using One-Way ANOVA to assess differences across age and service tenure. While brand reputation strongly influenced satisfaction and loyalty, ANOVA results showed limited statistically significant differences between demographic groups. This suggests a consistent

perception of brand-related outcomes across the sample. In South Africa's competitive mobile network operator market, the findings offer strategic insights into how Vodacom fosters customer relationships through brand perception to reduce churn and enhance loyalty.

1. Introduction

The South African telecommunications industry requires robust brand management, as Mobile Network Operators (MNOs) face intense competition and high customer churn rates (Sutherland, 2021; Hawthorne & Grzybowski, 2019). Corporate brand reputation shapes stakeholder perceptions and competitiveness, evolving from functional to emotional value (Kato & Tsuda, 2018; Kato, 2021). MNOs must leverage social media and corporate social responsibility to enhance brand strength, with continuous investment in brand strategy being essential amid digital transformation.

This study examines customer perceptions of corporate brand reputation as a strategic tool for retention in South Africa's mobile network operator (MNO) sector. It examines the impact of brand reputation on loyalty, satisfaction, and retention to refine retention strategies.

Prior research highlights the role of customer retention in driving revenue growth. Pfeifer & Farris (2004) emphasize the cost-effectiveness of multichannel marketing and retention, a finding supported by Afsar, Qureshi, & Shahjehan (2010) and Hoang & Nguyen (2019). Amini et al. (2012) assert that a strong corporate image fosters confidence, repeat business, positive word of mouth, and cost-effective retention.

This research addresses an empirical gap in South Africa's mobile network operator (MNO) industry, focusing on Vodacom customers. By integrating existing studies with new insights, it deepens the understanding of the role of brand reputation in loyalty and retention. Beyond academia, findings inform MNO strategies. Understanding customer retention drivers helps refine services, improve satisfaction, and foster stronger relationships. Tailored approaches enhance market positioning and ensure long-term success.

This study employed online surveys to evaluate Vodacom's corporate brand reputation and its influence on customer loyalty, satisfaction, and retention in a competitive market. Findings highlighted Vodacom's reputation within South Africa's mobile telecommunications sector (Balmer & Gray, 2003; Anismova, 2007; Alwi & Kitchen, 2014). Research frameworks provided insights into customer loyalty and satisfaction, shaping key research questions.

South Africa's mobile network industry has evolved significantly since Vodacom's establishment in 1992, alongside MTN, followed by Cell C and Telkom. Vodacom leads in active SIM cards, with post-paid subscriptions making up 20% of the market (Morgan & Govender, 2017). Traditionally, corporate brand reputation focused on functional attributes, but emotional and intangible aspects remained underexplored. This research aimed to bridge that gap, offering a deeper understanding of reputation in South Africa's mobile network sector (Hermiyenti & Wardi, 2018).

According to Anwar & Gulzar (2011), Aghekyan-Simonian, Forsythe, Suk Kwon and Catamaran (2012), Sari & Djatikusuma (2013), and He, Sha, and Yang (2013) as cited in Hermiyenti & Wardi (A literature review on the influence of promotion, price and brand image to purchase decision, 2018) Brand image was identified as a mediating variable that significantly influenced purchase decisions, shaping consumers' perceptions of a specific product. It encompasses the overall perceptions of a product based on consumer understanding of product information, helping consumers identify their needs and desires while distinguishing the product from others.

Corporate brand reputation, often referred to as reputational or organizational image, was defined as the overall impression that people hold of a corporation, encompassing their knowledge and beliefs. It influenced stakeholder perception as a whole, playing a pivotal role in establishing a cohesive corporate identity. A positive and robust corporate brand reputation bolstered credibility, attracted customers, and set the organization apart from competitors (Lievens, 2017; Kato & Tsuda, 2018).

Corporate brand reputation included the impact of functional quality and emotional attributes on the organization's character. Emotional attributes were recognized to play a

more significant role than functional attributes, particularly in shaping brand loyalty. A shift from focusing on functional attributes to emotional attributes in brand management was noted (Kato, 2021).

Customer satisfaction was defined as the overall perception of customers toward a company, influenced by their experiences and expectations, including emotional responses. Previous studies have identified a correlation between customer satisfaction, repurchasing behavior, and positive word-of-mouth. Research conducted in various markets identified different factors influencing customer satisfaction (Levesque & McDougall, 1996; Oliver, 1997; Zineldin, 2000; Davis, Kelley, & Hoffman, 1993).

Customer loyalty was considered significant as it required less effort for a company to generate repeat business from existing customers. Loyalty can be Platform 2d to the organization itself, its products, or its brand, and may stem from various factors, including previous experiences with any of these elements. Loyalty was explored from both an attitudinal and behavioural perspective, with attitudinal loyalty representing emotional connections and commitment (Morgan & Govender, 2017; Afsar et al., 2010; Plunkett et al., 2019).

Customer retention refers to a business's ability to maintain its client base over time, influenced by emotional factors and behavioural intentions (Oliver, 1997; Hansemark & Albinsson, 2004; Zineldin, 2006; Alshurideh, 2016). It is measured by tracking returning customers within a set period (Braer, 2020).

Business theory prioritizes retention over acquisition due to cost-effectiveness and long-term benefits (Weinstein, 2002). Studies show a 10% investment in retention can yield up to 30% more revenue (Afsar et al., 2010; Chang & Zhang, 2016; Hoang & Nguyen, 2019).

In the Mobile Network Operator (MNO) sector, churn refers to customers switching from one provider to another. Mobile number portability (MNP), introduced in 2006, reduced switching costs, making retention strategies critical, especially amid evolving market dynamics such as COVID-19 (NumberPortabilityCompany, 2020).

Customer retention enhances profitability, particularly in high-churn industries such as

mobile network operators (MNOs) (Schultz, 2017). Scholars define retention as continued loyalty despite potential switching factors, fostering mutual benefits for businesses and consumers (Oliver, 1997; Alshurideh, 2016; Hansemark & Albinsson, 2004; Zineldin, 2006).

A historical perspective highlights the importance of considering both functional and emotional attributes in corporate brand reputation (Pinochet et al., 2018). While functional attributes have been widely studied, emotional aspects remain less explored, particularly within the context of this study (Kato, 2021).

Corporate brand reputation is defined as a company's perceived values and reputation (Lievens, 2017; Kato & Tsuda, 2018; Balmer et al., 2020). This study emphasizes the emotional and intangible elements that shape brand identity and explores factors influencing customer satisfaction, including expectation alignment, perceived quality, trust, commitment, and service recovery (Afsar et al., 2010; Plunkett et al., 2019; Agyeiwaah et al., 2022).

Customer retention refers to maintaining existing customers over time, shaped by emotional and behavioural factors (Oliver, 1997; Hansemark & Albinsson, 2004). Studies highlight its cost-effectiveness compared to acquisition, with retention efforts driving long-term revenue growth (Weinstein, 2002; Pfeifer & Farriss, 2004). In MNO industries, high churn rates—especially post mobile number portability (MNP)—underscore the need for strong retention strategies (NumberPortabilityCompany, 2020). By fostering loyalty and engagement, businesses can enhance profitability and sustain customer commitment in the face of market challenges (Schultz, 2017).

Research Gap in Corporate Brand Reputation within South Africa's MNO Industry

- Existing studies in South Africa focus on rebranding, customer equity, loyalty, retention strategies, innovation, and customer experience.
- Limited research examines the impact of corporate brand reputation on client satisfaction, loyalty, and retention in the telecommunications sector.
- Most literature emphasizes functional branding over attitudinal reputation dimensions.

- International research covers brand reputation across industries but does not directly apply to South Africa’s mobile network operator (MNO) landscape.
- The findings will help industry practitioners refine their strategies and improve customer relationship management.
- Closing this gap enhances academic knowledge while supporting competitive positioning in South Africa’s mobile network operator (MNO) sector.
- Further research is needed, and developing a tailored theoretical framework could improve understanding in this specific market context.

2. Conceptual Framework

The study has adapted an existing conceptual model by Chigwendi (2020). This model is designed to clarify and explain the hypothesized relationships, as shown in Figure 2.1. It develops an understanding of the proposed connections between different elements. This research investigates the connections between customer loyalty (the dependent variable) and two independent variables: customer satisfaction and corporate brand reputation. The research aimed to understand how these independent variables collectively influence customer loyalty.

Figure 2.1: Conceptual Framework

Source: Adapted by the study from an existing framework by Chigwendi (2020).

Research Objectives

1. To investigate the association between corporate brand reputation and satisfaction, loyalty, and customer retention.
2. To analyse the effect of corporate brand reputation on client satisfaction.
3. To investigate the effect of corporate brand reputation and customer loyalty.
4. To assess the influence of corporate brand reputation on customer retention.
5. To examine the impact of client satisfaction on customer retention.
6. To investigate the influence of client satisfaction on customer loyalty.
7. To explore the impact of customer loyalty on customer retention.

3. Methodology

The research methodology in this study was grounded in a positivist approach, emphasizing the use of numerical data and statistical methods to analyse and understand the factors influencing corporate brand reputation among customers (Aliaga & Gunderson, 2002). The study followed the research onion framework introduced by Saunders et al. in 2009, as referenced by Daum (2012), which provided a structured approach for research methodology. Key steps in this quantitative research process included formulating a problem statement, generating hypotheses, reviewing relevant literature, conducting quantitative data analysis, and drawing conclusions to either support or reject the hypotheses, aligning with the approach outlined by Williams (2011).

Gilbert (2019) estimated that smartphone market penetration in South Africa was approximately 51%, with 40% owning basic phones and around 9% having no mobile phones at all. To estimate the population size for this study, the smartphone penetration rate of 51% was applied to the total population of 60,414,495 (Worldometer, 2023), resulting in a population of 30,829,482 individuals with smartphones. Adjusting for the penetration rate yields an estimated population of 20.1 million, including those under 18 years old. Subtracting 37% for those under 18 (Statista, 2019), the mobile network operator population is approximately 12.6 million. Vodacom customers accounted for

approximately 43.8% of the market (Labuschagne, 2024). The estimated population is therefore 5.5 million

Table 1: Sample Frame

			Actual Sample Collected	
Actual Population	Actual Data collected	Actual Sample Utilised	Platform 2dIn	Platform 1ook
5.5mil	398	389	280	109

Source: study calculation using SPSS.

Raosoft, a recognized authority in sample size calculation, recommends a minimum sample size of 385 respondents with a 5% margin of error and a 95% confidence level. This ensures reliable and meaningful findings (RAOSOFT, 2004). This guideline contributes to the accuracy and generalisability of the results.

Non-probability sampling, specifically convenience sampling, was employed due to geographical proximity, respondent availability, and willingness to participate. Convenience sampling aligns with South Africa's Protection of Personal Information Act (POPIA), ensuring responsible handling of personal data and compliance with stringent data protection regulations. This method respects privacy rights and adheres to legal standards in the processing of sensitive information.

An online survey was developed to gather first-hand, specific information aligned with the research objectives. This method ensured original data collection directly from targeted participants, allowing them to share their opinions and experiences. Thoughtfully constructed survey questions produced relevant insights, minimizing dependence on pre-existing data.

Secondary data involved exploring a variety of credible sources from both local and international contexts, including government organizations, occupational associations, media outlets, and academic journals. These sources provided authoritative, current, and focused perspectives, enhancing the research with multiple viewpoints.

This study employed a five-section survey to investigate customer perceptions and behaviours in South Africa's mobile network operator (MNO) sector. Section A covered demographics, Section B corporate brand reputation, Section C client satisfaction, Section D customer loyalty, and Section E retention strategies.

Ethical principles included informed consent, confidentiality, voluntary participation, accurate representation, and prevention of harm. A university pre-approval process ensured compliance, supporting responsible research practices.

The study employed confirmatory factor analysis (CFA), correlation analysis, and structural equation modelling (SEM) to validate the constructs. SPSS and SPSS Amos version 22 were used for statistical analysis, ensuring the credibility of the results.

Various methods were used to ensure the credibility and accuracy of the research instrument.

- Face Validity: Sections focused on customer perceptions, capturing past experiences and sentiments.
- Content Validity: Questions addressed both current and historical information, enabling measurement against the provided theory.
- Criterion Validity: Reducing the number of questions ensured accurate data collection.
- Convergent Validity: Compared new instruments with established scales for corporate brand reputation, satisfaction, loyalty, and customer retention.
- Discriminant Validity: Verified that each construct was uniquely represented, though some overlap among constructs posed challenges.
- Cronbach's Alpha: Ensured internal consistency, enhancing credibility and validity
- Composite Reliability: Assessed internal consistency within each construct.
- Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) employed factor loading and composite reliability to validate constructs. Structural Equation Modelling (SEM) used model fit indices (CFI, RMSEA, SRMR) and path coefficients to analyse relationships among constructs.

4. Data Analysis and Findings

A total of 398 responses were received via online completion for the survey. However, 9 of these respondents were not Vodacom users and their responses were excluded from the analysis. As a result, the analysis was based on 389 complete responses, which exceeded the minimum requirement of 385 as calculated using the Raosoft software. The sample included respondents from both Platform 1 and Platform 2, with 109 responses from Platform 2 and 280 from Platform 1.

A total of 398 responses were received via online completion for the survey. However, 9 of these respondents were not Vodacom users and their responses were excluded from the analysis. As a result, the analysis was based on 389 complete responses, which exceeded the minimum requirement of 385 as calculated using the Raosoft software. The sample included respondents from both Platform 1 and Platform 2, with 109 responses from Platform 2 and 280 from Platform 1.

For corporate brand reputation, customer satisfaction, and loyalty, the minimum value in this dataset is 1.35, 1.05, and 1.06, respectively, while the maximum value is 5. The extent of data variability is calculated by the difference between the maximum and minimum values (Corporate brand reputation: $5 - 1.35 = 3.65$; Customer satisfaction: $5 - 1.05 = 3.95$; Loyalty: $5 - 1.06 = 3.94$). This wide range means a higher degree of variability exists within this dataset.

The study utilized 389 surveys. For corporate brand reputation, client satisfaction, loyalty, and retention, minimum values were 1.83, 1.83, 1.40, and 1.00, respectively, with a maximum of 5. Data variability ranged from 3.17 to 4, indicating diverse responses. This broad range enhances insights, identifies customer segments, and supports targeted strategies. Wide variability in human studies reflects real-world diversity, enriching analysis.

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics

Descriptive Statistics

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation	Skewness		Kurtosis	
	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Std. Error	Statistic	Std. Error
Corporate Brand Reputation	389	1.83	5.00	4.38	.693	-1.264	.124	1.339	.247
Customer Satisfaction	389	1.83	5.00	4.25	.761	-1.113	.124	.810	.247
Customer Loyalty	389	1.40	5.00	4.28	.844	-1.254	.124	.973	.247
Customer Retention	389	1.00	5.00	4.20	.911	-1.322	.124	1.259	.247
Valid N (listwise)	389								

Source: AMOS output

Descriptive statistics suggest an approximate normal distribution. Skewness values range from -2 to 2, and kurtosis falls within -7 to 7, meeting accepted thresholds. Minimal asymmetry ensures balanced distribution around the mean. Proper kurtosis levels confirm no extreme tail effects, enhancing statistical reliability for inferential analyses.

Factor loading offers insights into the degree to which each indicator efficiently measures its associated hidden construct. Factor loadings range from 0 to 1 with 1 indicating high correlation within the underlying factors (Mishra, 2016). Table 4.2 underscores the intensity and validity of the pruned model. The high factor loadings, AVE values above 0.5 CR values greater than 0.7 and Cronbach's Alpha values above 0.7 collectively affirm the model's excellent convergent validity, reliability, and internal consistency. These findings provide a solid foundation for further statistical analyses and interpretations, enhancing the credibility of the study's results and supporting the validity of the conclusions drawn from the research.

Table 3: Final construct, Cronbach's Alpha, CR and AVE

Item		Factor Loading	Cronbach's alpha	CR (composi	AVE (average

				te reliabilit y)	variable extracted)
Corporate Brand Reputation			.878	0.882	0.555
cbr1	My mobile service provider is trustworthy	.751			
cbr2	My mobile service provider does business in an ethical manner	.802			
cbr3	My Mobile service has a good reputation	.725			
cbr4	My mobile service provider shop has a well-organized layout.	.781			
cbr5	The atmosphere of the mobile service providers shop is excellent	.746			
cbr6	My mobile service providers shop has attractive décor	.657			
Customer Satisfaction			.876	0.879	0.549
cs1	When you visit your mobile service, providers store you do not wait for a long time	.628			
cs2	When you contact your mobile service provider customer service department your problem was solved timeously	.738			
cs3	My mobile service provider meets my expectations	.734			
cs4	My mobile service provider network offers good coverage	.802			

cs5	My mobile service provider offers good quality for voice calls	.725			
cs6	My mobile service provider has fast internet connectivity	.805			
Customer Loyalty			.897	0.899	0.641
cl1	I will recommend my mobile network service provider to my friends and relations	.816			
cl2	I have only positive things to say about my mobile network provider	.745			
cl3	I consider my mobile network provider to be the best choice	.850			
cl4	If I were starting again, I would choose my current mobile network service provider	.791			
cl5	I am loyal to my mobile network provider	.798			
Customer Retention			.853	0.855	0.663
cr4	I will stay with my network even if other network providers have cheaper call rates	.787			
cr5	I will stay with my network even if other network providers have promotional activities	.860			
cr6	I have not considered changing my service provider	.793			

Source: AMOS output

Figure 4.1: Pruned Hypothesized CFA Model; Source: AMOS output

The model fit indices after pruning the model show that almost all indices fell within the accepted range for acceptable model fit. This means that the model was a good fit for the data. These results are outlined in Table 4.3.

Table 4: Pruned Model - Model Fit Indices

Absolute Fit Indexes	Acceptable Value	Value	Outcome
GFI	>0.9	0.902	Acceptable
AGFI	>0.9	0.874	Outside the acceptable range
RSMEA	<0.08	0.066	Acceptable
NFI	>0.9	0.919	Acceptable
NNFI (TLI)	>0.9	0.939	Acceptable
CFI	>0.9	0.948	Acceptable
CMIN/DF	< 5	2.673	Acceptable
SRMR	≤0.08	0.030	Acceptable

Source: AMOS output

Objective 1: To investigate the association between corporate brand reputation and satisfaction, loyalty, and customer retention.

H0: No significant relationships exist between corporate brand reputation, satisfaction, loyalty, and customer retention.

H1: Significant relationships exist among these constructs.

Ratings (Table 4) show **Corporate Brand Reputation** (mean = 4.38 ± 0.693) ranked highest, followed by **Customer Loyalty** (4.28 ± 0.844), **Customer Satisfaction** (4.25 ± 0.761), and **Customer Retention** (4.20 ± 0.911). Correlation analysis (Table 5) confirms significant associations, with **p-values** < **0.05** and correlation coefficients exceeding **0.5**.

Key findings:

1. **Corporate Brand Reputation** strongly influences **Customer Satisfaction** ($\beta = 0.902$, $t = 11.668$, $p < 0.001$) and **Customer Loyalty** ($\beta = 0.312$, $t = 3.162$, $p = 0.002$).
2. **Customer Satisfaction** significantly impacts **Customer Loyalty** ($\beta = 0.647$, $t = 5.989$, $p < 0.001$).
3. **Corporate Brand Reputation** and **Customer Satisfaction** do not directly affect **Customer Retention** ($p > 0.05$).
4. **Customer Loyalty** has a strong positive effect on **Customer Retention** ($\beta = 0.926$, $t = 4.966$, $p < 0.001$).

These results reject the **null hypothesis (H0)** and support **H1**, showing strong interconnections, except for direct effects of **Corporate Brand Reputation** and **Customer Satisfaction** on **Customer Retention**.

Table 5: Descriptive Statistics and Correlation Analysis

	Mean	Std. Deviation	1.	2.	3.	4.
1. Corporate Brand Reputation	4.38	.693	1			
2. Customer Satisfaction	4.25	.761	.800**	1		
3. Customer Loyalty	4.28	.844	.802**	.826**	1	
4. Customer Retention	4.20	.911	.614**	.676**	.735**	1

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Source: AMOS output

Table 6: Regression Weights

Hypotheses / Path Analysis		Weights	T-value	P-Value	R-Square
		Standardised			
Corporate Brand Reputation	—> Customer Satisfaction	.902	11.668	<0.001	.814
Corporate Brand Reputation	—> Customer Loyalty	.312	3.162	.002	.881
Customer Satisfaction	—> Customer Loyalty	.647	5.989	<0.001	
Corporate Brand Reputation	—> Customer Retention	-.254	-1.796	.073	.708
Customer Satisfaction	—> Customer Retention	.148	.793	.428	
Customer Loyalty	—> Customer Retention	.926	4.966	<0.001	
SEM Fit Indices: $\chi^2 = (438.392)$; $\chi^2/df = 2.673$; RMSEA = .066; CFI = .948. TLI = .939; AGFI = .874; GFI = .902; NFI = .919. ***P < 0.001					

Source: AMOS output

Objective 2: To analyse the influence of corporate brand reputation on client satisfaction.

H02: Corporate brand reputation does not affect client satisfaction.

H2: The effect of corporate brand reputation on client satisfaction is significant.

Table 6 shows that Corporate Brand Reputation ($\beta = 0.902$, t-value = 11.668, p-value < 0.001) positively and significantly affected client satisfaction. The effect was positive

because the coefficient for Corporate Brand Reputation ($\beta = 0.902$) was greater than zero. It was also significant because the p-value (< 0.001) was less than 0.05. This means the null hypothesis is rejected in favour of the alternative hypothesis. It can thus be concluded that corporate brand reputation has a positive and significant effect on client satisfaction.

Objective 3: To investigate influence of corporate brand reputation and customer loyalty.

H03: Corporate brand reputation has no effect on customer loyalty.

H3: The effect of corporate brand reputation on customer loyalty is significant.

Table 6 shows that Corporate Brand Reputation ($\beta = 0.312$, t-value = 3.162, p-value = 0.002) positively and significantly affected customer loyalty. The effect was positive because the coefficient for Corporate Brand Reputation ($\beta = 0.312$) was greater than zero. It was also significant because the p-value (0.002) was less than 0.05. This means the null hypothesis is rejected in favour of the alternative hypothesis. It can thus be concluded that corporate brand reputation has a positive and significant effect on customer loyalty.

Objective 4: To assess the influence of corporate brand reputation in influencing customer retention.

H04: Corporate brand reputation has no effect on customer retention.

H4: The effect of corporate brand reputation on customer retention is significant.

Table 6 shows that Corporate Brand Reputation ($\beta = -0.254$, t-value = -1.796, p-value = 0.073) had an insignificant effect on customer retention. The effect was insignificant because the p-value (0.073) was greater than 0.05. This means that the null hypothesis could not be rejected. It can be concluded that there is insufficient evidence at a 5% significance level to suggest that the impact of corporate brand reputation on influencing customer retention is significant.

Objective 5: To examine the impact of client satisfaction on customer retention.

H05: Customer satisfaction has no effect on customer retention.

H5: There is a significant impact of client satisfaction on customer retention.

Table 6 shows that Customer Satisfaction ($\beta = 0.148$, t-value = 0.793, p-value = 0.073) had an insignificant effect on customer retention. The effect was insignificant because the p-value (0.428) was greater than 0.05. This means that the null hypothesis could not be rejected. It can be concluded that there is no sufficient evidence at the 5% significance level to suggest that client satisfaction has a significant impact on customer retention.

Objective 6: To investigate the influence of client satisfaction on customer loyalty.

H06: Customer satisfaction has no effect on customer loyalty.

H6: The influence of client satisfaction on customer loyalty is significant.

Table 6 shows that Customer Satisfaction ($\beta = 0.647$, t-value = 5.989, p-value < 0.001) positively and significantly affected customer loyalty. The effect was positive because the coefficient for client satisfaction ($\beta = 0.647$) was greater than zero. It was also significant because the p-value (< 0.001) was less than 0.05. This means the null hypothesis is rejected in favour of the alternative hypothesis. It can thus be concluded that client satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on customer loyalty.

Objective 7: To explore the impact of customer loyalty on customer retention.

H07: Customer Loyalty has no effect on Customer Retention.

H6: The influence of Customer Loyalty on Customer Retention is significant.

Table 6 shows that Customer Loyalty ($\beta = 0.926$, t-value = 4.966, p-value < 0.001) positively and significantly affected Customer Retention. The effect was positive because the coefficient for Customer Loyalty ($\beta = 0.926$) was greater than zero. It was also significant because the p-value (< 0.001) was less than 0.05. This means the null hypothesis is rejected in favour of the alternative hypothesis. It can thus be concluded that Customer Loyalty has a positive and significant effect on Customer Retention.

5. Discussion & Conclusion

The study confirms significant relationships among corporate brand reputation, client satisfaction, and customer loyalty in South Africa's mobile network industry, particularly among Vodacom customers. While corporate brand reputation had no direct effect on retention, it showed a strong positive correlation with client satisfaction, consistent with Da Silve and Syed Alwi (2008), Tu and Chin (2013), and Kato and Tsuda (2018), who highlight that favourable brand perceptions enhance satisfaction. The findings diverge from those of Chigwendu (2020), which found no significant relationship between corporate brand reputation and client satisfaction in Zimbabwe's mobile network market. However, the study confirms a strong positive correlation between corporate brand reputation and customer loyalty, aligning with Pinochet et al. (2018), Lee & Lee (2018), Kato & Tsuda (2018), and Kato (2021). This contrasts with Chigwendu's (2020) findings, which did not support this connection in Zimbabwe. Additionally, client satisfaction showed a significant positive association with customer loyalty, consistent with Morgan & Govender (2017) in South Africa, Bhatti & Hassan (2019) in Australia, and Chigwendu (2020) in Zimbabwe, all reinforcing the strong link between satisfaction and loyalty in telecommunications.

Furthermore, the study confirms a strong positive correlation between corporate brand reputation and customer satisfaction, aligning with research by Da Silve & Syed Alwi (2008), Tu & Chin (2013), and Kato & Tsuda (2018). These studies emphasize that favourable brand perception enhances satisfaction with services. Chigwendu (2020) also examined this relationship in the MNO sector, finding a significant connection, despite contextual variations. This further reinforces the role of corporate brand reputation in shaping client satisfaction. Collectively, these findings highlight corporate brand reputation's critical influence in competitive markets like mobile telecommunications. A strong reputation not only boosts satisfaction but also builds trust and loyalty, essential for customer retention.

Findings reveal a significant positive association between client satisfaction and customer loyalty within the mobile network industry. It is widely studied that consumers tend to develop loyalty towards their service provider because of high levels of client satisfaction (Da Silve & Syed Alwi, 2008; Tu & Chin, 2013; Rendón et al., 2017). This relationship is underscored by research specific to the telecommunications sector, including studies by Morgan & Govender (2017) in South Africa, Bhatti & Hassan (2019) in Australia Chigwendi (2020) in Zimbabwe. Morgan and Govender's (2017) research focused on the S.A. telecommunications industry, highlighting a significant correlation between client satisfaction and loyalty among service providers. Similarly, Bhatti and Hassan (2019) explored the Australian telecommunications market and found substantial evidence supporting the linkage between client satisfaction and customer loyalty. Chigwendi (2020) delved into the telecommunications sector in Zimbabwe, confirming a significant relationship between these two factors. These studies collectively underscore the strong nature of the relationship between client satisfaction and customer loyalty across different contexts within the telecommunications industry. They highlight that satisfied customers are more inclined to demonstrate loyalty to their service providers, which is crucial for reducing churn rates and fostering long-term profitability and sustainability.

The study revealed that corporate brand reputation does not significantly influence customer retention at the 5% significance level. This contrasts with Oliver (1997), Hansemark & Albinsson (2004), Zineldin (2006), and Alshurideh (2016), who argue that a strong corporate brand reinforces positive perceptions and repeat business. This discrepancy highlights the complexity of customer retention dynamics in competitive industries like telecommunications. While brand reputation shapes perceptions and initial choices, long-term retention is likely driven by service quality, competitive pricing, and customer service excellence. In conclusion, despite the study's findings, theoretical frameworks still emphasize the importance of brand management and satisfaction strategies in building lasting customer relationships.

The study found no significant relationship between client satisfaction and customer retention, failing to reject the null hypothesis. This contrasts with Davis, Kelley & Hoffman (1993), Rendón et al. (2017), and Solimum & Fernandes (2018), who emphasize satisfaction's role in repurchasing behavior and word-of-mouth marketing. Davis, Kelley & Hoffman (1993) showed that satisfied customers exhibit loyalty through repeat

purchases and advocacy. Rendón et al. (2017) reinforced this in telecommunications, linking satisfaction to reduced churn and higher customer lifetime value. Solimum & Fernandes (2018) highlighted satisfied customers as revenue stabilizers and brand ambassadors, attracting new clients.

The discrepancy suggests that multiple factors, including service quality, pricing, and technological advancements, influence customer retention. Satisfaction alone may not guarantee retention, especially in competitive industries like telecommunications. Despite strong literature support for satisfaction's role in retention, this study underscores the complexity of retention strategies. Future research should explore additional influencing factors across diverse markets to refine retention models

The analysis confirms a significant positive effect of client satisfaction on customer loyalty, supported by key theories:

- Expectation Confirmation Theory (ECT) – Loyalty increases when customer expectations are met or exceeded (Hun et al., 2019).
- Relationship Marketing Theory – Long-term relationships and personalized interactions strengthen loyalty (Plunkett et al., 2019).
- Social Exchange Theory – Loyalty is influenced by the perceived balance of benefits and costs in business interactions (Afsar et al., 2010).
- Brand Relationship Quality (BRQ) – Emotional, social, and psychological connections deepen brand loyalty (Plunkett et al., 2019).

These frameworks emphasize how meeting expectations, building relationships, balancing benefits, and cultivating emotional connections lead to stronger loyalty. Additionally, customer loyalty has a significant impact on customer retention, as noted by Morgan & Govender (2017) and Plunkett et al. (2019). Theories such as ECT, Relationship Marketing, and Social Exchange underscore the importance of aligning experiences with expectations, personalized engagement, and value-driven interactions for long-term retention. Findings also suggest that satisfaction alone does not guarantee loyalty, highlighting the necessity for a multifaceted approach to customer retention.

The study confirms a strong positive effect of customer loyalty on customer retention, backed by Morgan & Govender (2017), who highlight loyalty's role in repeat business. Plunkett et al. (2019) further define behavioral loyalty as consistent purchasing patterns, reinforcing brand confidence and higher retention rates.

Theoretical Perspectives:

- Expectation Confirmation Theory (ECT) – Meeting initial expectations fosters loyalty and retention (Hun et al., 2019).
- Relationship Marketing Theory – Personalized experiences and long-term relationships strengthen loyalty (Plunkett et al., 2019).
- Social Exchange Theory – Balancing benefits and costs enhances retention (Afsar et al., 2010). However, satisfaction alone does not guarantee loyalty, suggesting additional influencing factors.

Both empirical evidence and theoretical frameworks highlight customer loyalty's critical role in retention strategies. Studies reinforce the need for aligning experiences, personalized engagement, and value-driven interactions to effectively retain customers.

Feel free to send more content, and I'll keep refining efficiently!

Based on the insights obtained, an accepted framework has been established for this study, as depicted in Figure 5.1. The analysis highlights the significant role of corporate brand image in shaping customer satisfaction, strengthening loyalty, and enhancing

retention. Findings also indicate that brand image has a direct influence on loyalty, thereby contributing to customer retention.

This research offers valuable insights into the relationship between corporate brand reputation, satisfaction, and loyalty within South Africa's mobile network industry, particularly among Vodacom customers.

While a strong brand reputation fosters satisfaction and loyalty, its direct impact on retention was not found to be significant. These results emphasize that, while brand perception is crucial, additional factors beyond reputation alone may influence customer retention.

Figure 5.1: Accepted Framework; Source: Composed by this study

Limitations include reliance on Platform 2dIn and Platform 1ook users, which may potentially bias the results toward tech-savvy and socially engaged individuals, while excluding other consumer groups. Regional and demographic differences may limit the study's applicability beyond Vodacom customers in South Africa. Additionally, self-reported data introduces response bias and subjective interpretations, requiring caution when generalizing findings across telecom markets.

Future research could explore:

- Service quality, pricing, and technological advancements in customer retention.
- Demographic factors like income and usage patterns to refine retention strategies.
- Deeper segmentation for targeted customer insights.

- Longitudinal studies tracking market evolution and changing consumer expectations.
- Expanding research in these areas would enhance practical strategies for improving loyalty and retention in competitive industries.

References

- Ab Hamid, S. N., WAN JUSOH, W. J., & MAULAN, S. (2020). CORPORATE BRAND IMAGE OF ISLAMIC BANK IN MALAYSIA: ANTECEDENTS AND CONSEQUENCE. *International Journal of Management Studies*, 27(1), 49-72.
- Abdolvand, N. (2015). Activity Level as a Link between Customer Retention and Customer Lifetime Value. *Iranian Journal of Management Studies*, 8(4), 568-587.
- Adamson, K. A., & Prion, S. (2013). Reliability: Measuring Internal Consistency Using Cronbach's alpha. *Clinical Simulation in Nursing*, 9, 179-180.
- Afsar, B., Qureshi, J. A., & Shahjehan, A. (2010). Determinants of customer loyalty in the banking sector. *African Journal of Business Management*, 4(6), 1040-1047.
- Agyeiwaah, E., Dayour, F., & Zhou, Y. (2022). How does employee commitment impact customers' attitudinal loyalty? *Journal of Hospitality and Tourism Insights*, 5(2), 350-376.
- Aliaga, M., & Gunderson, B. (2002). *Interactive Statistics*. Thousand Oaks: Sage Publications.
- Alwi, S. F., & Kitchen, P. J. (2014). Projecting corporate brand image and behavioral response in business schools: Cognitive or affective brand attributes? *Journal of Business research*, 67(11), 2324-2336.
- Amini, A., Darani, M., Afshani, M., & Amini, Z. (2012). Effectiveness of marketing strategies and corporate image on brand equity as a sustainable competitive advantage. *Interdisciplinary journal of contemporary research in business*, 4(2), pp.192-205. *Interdisciplinary journal of contemporary research in business*, 4(2), 192-205.
- Anismova, T. A. (2007). The effects of corporate brand attributes on attitudinal and behavioural consumer loyalty. *Journal of Consumer Marketing*, 24(7), 395-405.

- Balmer, J. M., & Gray, E. R. (2003). Corporate brands: What are they? What of them? , 37(7/8), 972 - 997. *European Journal of Marketing*, 37(8), 972-997.
- Bhatti, H. S., & Hassan, T. (2019). The influence of customer experience on customer loyalty for the mobile telecommunication service. CONF-IRM 2019 Proceedings.
- Central, T. (2023). *Tech Central*. Retrieved July 17, 2023, from <https://techcentral.co.za/mobile-market-share-in-south-africa-vodacom-mtn-telkom-and-cell-c/207433/>
- Chigwendi, S. (2020). Corporate brand image and switching behavior case of mobile telecommunications customers in Zimbabwe. *Innovative Marketing*, 80-87.
- Da Silve, R. V., & Syed Alwi, S. F. (2008). Online corporate brand image, satisfaction and loyalty. *Journal of Brand Management*, 16, 119-144.
- Das, S., Mishra, M., & Mohanty, P. K. (2018). The impact of customer relationship management (CRM) practices on customer retention and the mediating effect of customer satisfaction., 5(1), p.4. *International Journal of Management Studies*, 1(4), 95-103.
- Daum, P. (2012). A Strategic Approach for Raising Efficiencies in the Cross-Border Interaction Process. In *International Synergy Management* (pp. 33-35). Hamburg: Anchor Academic Publishing.
- Davis, M. A., Kelley, S. W., & Hoffman, D. (1993). A typology of retail failures and recoveries. *Journal of Retailing*, 69, 429-452.
- Dawi, N. M., Jusoh, A., Streimikis, A., & Mardani, A. (2018). The influence of service quality on customer satisfaction and customer behavioral intentions by moderating role of switching barriers in satellite pay TV market. *Economics & Sociology*, 11(4), 198-214.

- Dike, M., & Iddy, J. (2023). Competitive action-response strategies of mobile network operators in sub-Saharan Africa. *African Journal of Business Management*, 17(5), 84-95.
- Gao, L., Haan, E., Melero-Polo, I., & Sese, F. J. (2023). Winning your customers' minds and hearts: Disentangling the effects of lock-in and affective customer experience on retention, 51(2), pp.334-371. *Journal of the Academy of Marketing Science*, 51(2), 334-371.
- Glibert, P. (2019, April 3). *IT Web*. Retrieved 07 16, 2020, from <https://www.itweb.co.za/content/GxwQDM1AYy8MIPVo>
- Hair, J. F., Howard, M. C., & Nitzi, C. (2020). Assessing measurement model quality in PLS-SEM using confirmatory composite analysis. , 109, pp.101-110. *Journal of Business Research*, 109, 101-110.
- Hawthorne, R., & Grzybowski, L. (2019). Narrowing the digital divide: The role of complementarities between fixed and mobile data in South Africa. Munich: Munich Society for the Promotion of Economic Research.
- Hermiyenti, S., & Wardi, Y. (2018). A literature review on the influence of promotion, price and brand image to purchase decision. *Advances in Economics, Business and Management Research*, 64, 254-261.
- Kato, T. (2021). Functional value vs emotional value: A comparative study of the values that contribute to a preference for a corporate brand. *International Journal of Information Management Data Insights*, 1(2).
- Kato, T., & Tsuda, K. (2018). A Management Method of the Corporate Brand Image Based on Customers' Perception. *Procedia Computer Science* 126 (2018) 1368–1377, 126, 1368-1377.

- Lamm, A. J., & Lamm, K. W. (2019). Using non-probability sampling methods in agricultural and extension education research. *Journal of International Agricultural and Extension Education*, 26(1), 52-59.
- Lee, J., & Lee, Y. (2018). Effects of multi-brand company's CSR activities on purchase intention through a mediating role of corporate image and brand image. *Journal of Fashion Marketing and Management: An International Journal*, 22(3), 387-403.
- Levesque, T., & Mcdougall, G. H. (1996). Determinants of customer satisfaction in retail banking. *International Journal of Bank Marketing*, 17(1), 12-20.
- Lievens, F. (2017). Organizational Image. In *The SAGE Encyclopedia of Industrial and Organizational Psychology, 2nd* (pp. 2-5). Thousand Oaks: SAGE Publications, Inc.
- Magatef, S. G., & Tomalieh, E. F. (2015). The impact of customer loyalty programs on customer retention. *International Journal of Business and Social Science*, 6(8), 78-93.
- Mentz, H. (2011). CUSTOMER-BASED BRAND EQUITY OF THE MAJOR CELLPHONE NETWORK SERVICE PROVIDERS AMONGST PRINCIPAL ESTATE AGENTS IN THE GAUTENG PROVINCE OF SOUTH AFRICA. Tshwane: UNIVERSITY OF SOUTH AFRICA.
- Mishra, M. (2016). Confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) as an analytical technique to assess measurement error in survey research: A review. 20(2), pp.97-112. *Paradigm*, 20(2), 97-112.
- Morgan, S., & Govender, K. (2017). Exploring customer loyalty in the South African mobile telecommunications sector. *Cogent Business & Management*, 4, 1-16.

- Mosupyoe, S. S. (2011). THE IMPLICATIONS OF CORPORATE REBRANDING IN THE SOUTH AFRICAN MOBILE CELLULAR TELECOMMUNICATIONS SERVICE INDUSTRY: CHALLENGES AND OPPORTUNITIES. Tshwane: 1st International Conference on Accounting, Business and Economics.
- Mpwanyana, M. F., & Letsoalo, M. E. (2019). Relationship between Service Quality, Customer Satisfaction and Behavioural Intentions in South Africa's Mobile Telecommunication Industry. *African Journal of Business and Economic Research*, 14(2), 67-89.
- Mudanganyi, M., Muposhi, A., & Shanhuyenzva, R. M. (2019). The Influence of Customer-Based Brand Equity on Customer Satisfaction. *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF BUSINESS AND MANAGEMENT STUDIES*, 11(2), 32-42.
- Oliver, R. L. (1997). *Satisfaction: A behavioral perspective on the consumer*. New York: McGraw Hill.
- Pinochet, L. H., Lopes, E. L., Srulzon, C. H., & Onusic, L. M. (2018). The influence of the attributes of "internet of things" products on functional and emotional experiences of purchase intention. *Innovation & Management Review*, 15(3), 303-320.
- Plunkett, D., Fulthrop, K., & Paris, C. M. (2019). Examining the relationship between place attachment and behavioral loyalty in an urban park setting. *Journal of Outdoor Recreation and Tourism*, 25, 36-44.
- Rendón, C. M., Vásquez, A., Benjumea-Aria, M., & Valencia-Aria, A. (2017). Proposed model for measuring customer satisfaction with telecommunications services. *Mediterranean Journal of Social Sciences*, 8(2), 15-24.
- SA, S. (2023). *South African Government*. Retrieved September 11, 2023, from <https://www.gov.za/about-sa/south-africas->

- Tu, Y. T., & Chin, H. C. (2013). An empirical study of corporate brand image, customer perceived value and satisfaction on loyalty in shoe industry. *Journal of Economics and Behavioral Studies*, 5(7), 469-483.
- Ullman, J. B. (2006). Structural Equation Modeling: Reviewing the Basics and Moving Forward. *JOURNAL OF PERSONALITY ASSESSMENT*, 87(1), 35-50.
- van der Wal, R. W., Pampallis, A., & Bond, C. (2002). Service quality in a cellular telecommunications company: a South African experience. *Managing Service Quality: An International Journal*, 12(5), 323-335.
- Van Vaerenberg, Y., Orsingher, C., & Vermei, I. (2014). A meta-analysis of relationships linking service failure attributions to customer outcome. *Journal of Service Research*, 17(4), 381-396.
- Williams, C. (2011). Research methods. *Journal of Business & Economics Research*, 5(3), 65-70.
- Worldometer. (2023). *Worldometer*. Retrieved July 17, 2023, from <https://www.worldometers.info/world-population/south-africa-population/>
- Zineldin, M. (2000). *TRM: Total relationship management*. Lund: Student literature.

Endnotes

1. Vodacom was selected as the case study due to its market leadership and brand visibility in South Africa's mobile network operator sector.
2. The conceptual framework was adapted from Chigwendi (2020) to align with the South African context and research objectives.
3. Ethical clearance was obtained through a university pre-approval process, ensuring compliance with responsible research practices.

4. The use of convenience sampling was guided by accessibility and alignment with South Africa's POPIA regulations.

5. ANOVA were chosen for their robustness in validating latent constructs and assessing complex relationships.

6. The study's limitations include reliance on online platforms, which may skew the sample toward digitally engaged users.

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Data Availability Statement

The data that support the findings of this study are not publicly available due to privacy and ethical restrictions under South Africa's Protection of Personal Information Act (POPIA). Data may be made available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request and subject to institutional approval.